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Agricultural Development and Food Security in Nigeria, 2015-2023

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ABSTRACT

This study attempted a holistic examination of the overall impact of agricultural development on food security in Nigeria. The scope of the study spanned years, from 2015 to 2023. In the background to this study, the relevance of food as the most vital among the basic needs of humans was carefully identified and comprehensively appraised. The study however observed that over the years, the Nigerian state has witnessed a high level of economic deterioration in terms of the deepening state of food security crisis, having direct implication in high rate of excruciating hunger and concomitant rise in the level of malnutrition-related diseases. The study raised three research questions, as well as three research objectives to aid scientific inquiries. The study was anchored on the theory of Economic Determinism as propounded by Karl Marx. The study revealed that administrative lapses/incompetence, corruption and insecurity constitute the factors responsible for the declining state of agricultural development in Nigeria. It also revealed that high rate of food importation, high rate of poverty and hunger, and an attendant rise in malnutrition level and diseases, comprised the consequences of the sustained decline in agricultural development as it relates to food security in Nigeria. This study therefore rationalised that in order to revamp and reposition Nigeria's agricultural sector to secure a satisfactory level of food sufficiency, availability and accessibility, salient but proactive measures should be taken. The study recommended among other things for a statutorily-enabled mechanism for a transparent and effective process of agricultural policies implementation.

Keywords: Bureaucratic Structure, Constitution, Food Sufficiency, Institution, Policy

INTRODUCTION

Among the fundamental necessities of livelihood and human existence, food takes dominance and plays a preeminent role in defining and sustaining the physical health, fitness and survival of humans. Hence, every politically sovereign state prioritises food security as one of its cardinal social welfare responsibilities to the citizenry. The need for food security was evidently captured in section 16, sub-section 2(d) of the 1999 constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria (with amendments), when it impressed that state policy should be channeled towards ensuring that food is provided for all citizens in a suitable and adequate manner. Also, under the Fifth Constitutional Alteration Bill (No.65) of 2023, greater emphasis was made on the need for food security. In fact, the 2023 Alteration Bill as it pertains to food security embodies a clear amendment to section 16 of the 1999 constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria. Specifically, the point of distinction between section 16 of the 1999 constitution as it pertains to food security and the current Alteration Bill (no.65) of 2023, is that the latter considers food security as

constituting part of the inalienable rights of the citizenry, hence it should form part of the basic and essential social policies of government. The 2023 alteration bill on food security purportedly projects the humanitarian response of government to food availability for millions of hungry Nigerians (Nigerian Economic Summit Group, 2024). The statutory responsibility of government with regards to ensuring food security was echoed by Benson (2017). Thus:

In modern democratic practice, political sovereignty is neither attained by conquest nor by imposition; it is rather a product of the degree of responsiveness and answerability of the governing political class to the myriad of needs of the citizenry. Responsible governments world over, strive to secure the loyalty and cooperation of the people by fulfilling the fundamental tasks of governance like the provision of basic infrastructure, welfare services and security. (p.49)

A buoyant food security system of any sovereign state must always be anchored on a very fertile productive agricultural system. Therefore, to actualise the objective of performing satisfactorily, the statutory task of sustaining food security, governments of sovereign states revolutionise farming practices through well-determined and potent agricultural policies. Such policies are usually documents containing a compendium of detailed plan, proposals, ideas or guidelines which direct actions towards achieving intended objectives. Intensive and far-reaching agricultural policies should necessarily be accompanied with actionable strategies that may come in the form of comprehensive incentives to farmers and farming practices. Hence, such may include allocation of sufficient lands, provision of fertilizers, provision of mechanised implements, as well as other modern technologies relevant to modern farming practices, grants, agricultural extension services and programmes, etc. Nonetheless, the achievability of agricultural development through brilliantly-conceived agricultural policies must invariably be dependent on effective implementation processes. As such, the impact of political will and a viable but competent bureaucratic system cannot be either underestimated or substituted (Ezeoke, 2021).

Nigeria, being a country yearning for development, food sufficiency and security become critical to attaining an all-round socio-economic developmental stride. Undoubtedly, a vibrant and progressive macro-economic state is measured by the percentage of the health status of the working population. Hence, a physically, mentally and psychologically healthy population is a precondition for a buoyant national economy. No doubt, food and good nutrition are unavoidably and inseparably relevant to good health. In the wake of the knowledge of this fact, it should be incumbent on the Nigerian government to explore and exploit all the potentials inherent in good agricultural development policies to ensure an appreciable level of food sufficiency and security. The same cannot be said of the Nigerian state where the declining state of agricultural development has over time, led to an escalating trend of crisis associated with food availability and accessibility (Ahamba, 2020).

Over time, the Nigerian state has been engulfed in a deteriorating, bleak and very unfortunate economic condition, particularly characterised by an excruciating level of hunger. Hence, hunger, as being widely experienced in Nigeria is undoubtedly a direct product of lack of adequate food security. The lack of adequate food security in this context entails a combination of two-dimensional symptoms of lack of sufficiency and accessibility. On the other hand, the root cause of the ever-rising trends of lack of availability and accessibility is traceable to the poor and declining state of agricultural development in Nigeria. Hence, according to Tunji (2024), a recent survey by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), shows that up to 20.8% of Nigerian households have resorted to begging food or borrowing to buy food from either relatives or friends. Also, Tunji (2024) reported that the same recent NBS survey indicates that up to 65.8% Nigerian households are unable to afford a healthy and nutritious meal.

On account of the decadent state of agricultural development in Nigeria, successive governments have resorted to food importation as an alternative to the inability of the country to be food sufficient through massive food production. According to Ikokwu (2024), the report by the National Bureau of Statistics shows that in the year 2023, Nigeria spent over N2 trillion on food importation alone. Sadly, the huge

amount of money spent periodically on food importation and other commodities tend to impact negatively on Nigeria's terms of trade. Hence, such has continued to lead to trade deficits in the international market. The immediate fallout of this experience has always been manifesting in the continuous weakening of the naira against other foreign currencies like the dollar, euro and pounds sterling. Hence, in the opinion of Tunji (2024), on account of the fact that Nigeria's import by far, surpasses its export, the tendency for less demand of its currency becomes unavoidable. That, by simple economic calculation could be responsible for the continuous decline in the value of the naira, Therefore, the main thrust of this study is to establish a link between agricultural development and food security in Nigeria, covering periods from 2015 to 2024. The study developed three research questions and they include:

- i. What are the factors responsible for the declining state of agricultural development as it relates to food security in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023?
- ii. What are the consequences of the declining state of agricultural development as it pertains to food security in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023?
- iii. What measures should be taken to maximally improve agricultural development in Nigeria?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The study adopted the review research design. Through this approach, the study explored, through data generated from secondary sources, the nature and trends of agricultural development policies and programmes as they relate to food security in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023. Through this design, the study reviewed scholarly materials, newspaper reports and official documents on the current state of the nation with regards to food availability, sufficiency and accessibility; it comprehensively x-rayed the various limitations of agricultural development efforts, hence, prompting a threat to food security during the period under study.

Method of Data Collection: The study relied exclusively on the instrumentalisation of textbooks, journals, official documents and materials from the internet as sources through which data were generated.

Method of Data Analysis: The various data generated in this study were analysed qualitatively, using the content analysis method.

Conceptual Clarification

Agricultural Development

Agricultural development fundamentally entails an institutional effort, geared towards introducing some innovatory milestone, specifically aimed at boosting quality and sufficiency in food production. Whether it exists in the category of fish, poultry, crop or livestock farming, agricultural development typically connotes the idea of raising the bar with regards to bringing into existence, new or added knowledge, information, techniques or methods targeted at increasing the volume and quality of food production. "Development" as the name implies, stands for change, innovation, renovation, improvement, advancement, invention, evolution, expansion and emergence of new ideas and trends. When associated with 'agriculture', development in this context majorly explains an attempt at maximally increasing food production output. Agricultural development relevantly exists at both micro and macro levels. At the micro economic level, agricultural development may involve an effort by an individual to advance their subsistence farming practice, with a view to boosting food production for the sustainability of themselves and their immediate family. On the other hand, at the macro-economic level, agricultural development simply denotes an institutionally enabling effort by regional or national governments to maximally improve an integrated farming system that would stimulate massive output in agricultural production, simultaneously translating into sufficiency in food production. This is usually achieved through the initiation and enactment of very salient and potentially robust agricultural policies and implementable programmes (Osadebe, 2019; Agoda, 2022).

At the international scene, agricultural development represents a concerted effort by comity of nations to combat hunger and ensure adequate food security at sub-continental, continental and global levels. It is

usually a deliberate act of pulling resources together to ensure a coordinate collaborative and complementary assistance for member countries by engaging in, and aggressively but committedly funding large scale agricultural development initiatives, schemes and projects. Fundamentally, the aggregate involvement, as well as commitment by comity of nations around the globe to fund agricultural development initiatives and projects to boost sufficiency in food production, usually reflects a precautionary humanitarian intervention. Hence, it is usually incumbent on world leaders at the international scene to initiate and establish long-term agricultural development plans and strategies which, if translated into sufficiency in food production output, would be expected to provide a reliable aspect of humanitarian assistance to countries affected by natural disaster crisis like flood or earthquake, or involved in wars. The quest to save millions of human beings in the world, especially in third world countries of Asia and Africa from hunger, starvation or malnutrition, constitutes the most vital aspect of the multidimensional responsibilities of international organisations. Hence, member countries of international organisations at the sub-continental, continental and global levels like the Economic Community of West African States (Ecowas), African Union (AU), European Union (EU), North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO), United Nations (UN), etc. are statutorily required to make annual contributions to aid the funding of continental, inter-continental and global food production projects through major improvements in agricultural production (Ndukam, 2021).

According to Komolafe (2018), agricultural development entails an institutional resolve by the government of any sovereign politically organised entity to maximally improve the mode of food production through the introduction of mechanized system of farming. Corroboratively, Alawu (2020), impressed that agricultural development involves a deliberate shift from the traditional method of farming, to a more mechanised system, with a view to boosting food production to a sufficient and satisfactory level. Still in agreement with the two definitions captured above, Ezeoke (2021), informed that agricultural development particularly consists in the determined application of modern and technologically improved techniques and approaches to farming, which central objective is anchored on enhancing food production. In the opinion of Magaji (2020), agricultural development fundamentally refers to a deliberate adoption and application of new strategies, methods and techniques to producing food through farming practice. Therefore, in line with the various shades of ideas portrayed above, this study can confidently define agricultural development as the deliberate resort to embracing and implementing the various technologically improved methods and approaches to modern farming, which are critical to achieving a sustainable increase and sufficiency in food production.

Food Security

Food security generally refers to a social condition where people who live in any politically organised society can conveniently have access to sufficient, nutritious and affordable food at a limitless and sustainable period of time. Food security, when subjected to micro-economic and macro-economic analysis, collectively suggests that an individual person should be rightfully entitled to safe, nutritious and affordable meals over a steady and uninterrupted period of time. The macro-economic implication of the concept of food security strictly implies that access to sufficient, affordable and nutritious food on a sustainable basis should be all-encompassing, unbiased and non-selective. By this, it simply entails that the utilitarian principle-the latter which fundamentally advocates for the happiness and comfort of the greater majority in any given population, should guide food distribution and accessibility in a society. Sufficient food availability in any society, especially in a country capacity is usually an effort that is achieved through increased agricultural development practice or through greater reliance on importation. However, it has been observed that in order to achieve a sustainable level of food security, most politically independent states around the world usually opt for enhanced emphasis on national agricultural development (Agama, 2020)

According to Ahamba (2020), the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) provided an elaborate but comprehensive definition of the term, 'food security'. According to the agency:

Food security means having, at all times, both physical and economic access to sufficient food to meet dietary needs for a

productive and healthy life. A family is food secure when its members do not live in hunger or fear of hunger. Food insecurity is often rooted in poverty and has long-term impacts on the ability of families, communities and countries to develop and prosper. Prolonged undernourishment stunts growth, slows cognitive development and increases susceptibility to illness. (p. 93)

As earlier observed, the definition stated above by USAID embodies in its wholeness, everything that the concept of food security represents, both in theory and in practice. Hence, Ahamba (2020), in their attempt at analytically dissecting the concept of food security, implied that the absence of an institutionally guaranteed sustainability in food availability and accessibility can be likened to a condition of a seemingly absence of basic human development-the latter which is portrayed in the capacity of people to have an appreciable degree of access to the fundamental necessities of life. Based on the definition provided by World bank during a World Food Summit in 1996, food security is defined as a social situation that guarantees that people at all times should have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life. Thus, according to the 1996 World Food Summit, there are four main dimensions of food security and they include

- i. **Physical Availability of Food:** This is specifically concerned with the volume of food supply in any given society at any given period of time. This is usually measured and determined by the degree of food production and the level of food in stock and national food reserve.
- ii. **Economic and Physical Access to Food:** This aspect emphasises the fact that food availability must be linked with accessibility. Ordinarily, sufficient supply of food does not automatically imply that individuals or households have access to the supplied food items. In this wise, food production, food availability and food accessibility should be complementarily linked. Therefore, to achieve the objectives of food security through this medium, government's policy should be directed towards income review through wage increase and food prices control.
- iii. **Food Utilisation:** Under this, emphasis is always on the degree of the impact of food intake on the physical, mental and general health status of individuals in a society. In this context therefore, it is assumed that food security should connote the consumption of food with high nutritional value. This is because, food intake with the inherent characteristics of poor nutritional content may give rise to multi-related health issues
- iv. **The Sustainability of the Above-three Dimensions:** In this regard, the emphasis is on the continued maintenance of physical availability, accessibility and proper utilisation of food intake. An individual is considered to be food insecure when they cannot afford to interruptedly sustain an era of food availability, accessibility and the averagely high nutritional quality of meals. Thus, this is usually caused by loss of jobs and government policies that may give rise to inflation of food prices and dwindling of the income level of individuals in a society (Global Food and Nutrition Security Dashboard, 2024).

A Critical Assessment of the Nature of Agricultural Development in Nigeria, vis-à-vis its Impact on Food Security

Agricultural development in Nigeria can trace its origin to the colonial era when the enormous proceeds from farming activities prompted the initiation of policies and programmes to expand and sustain the seemingly evident gains of engagement in agricultural practices. The agricultural sector in the 1960s, contributed up to 85% of Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings and about 90% value-chain employment opportunities. Also, the sector, at Nigeria's independence in 1960 was said to be contributing up to 60% of the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The achievement of the above-mentioned feat was the

result of the gains recorded in the various giant agricultural activities and research schemes undertaken by the British colonial government at the time. Hence, in 1893, the British colonial government established the first agricultural research institute in Nigeria, known as the Department of Botanical Research in the western region. Motivated by this development, in 1905, the British colonial administration, under the platform of the British Cotton Growers Association, acquired 10.35 square kilometres of land for growing of cotton. Following the amalgamation of the northern and southern protectorates in 1914, in 1921, the British colonial government created a unified department of agriculture. In 1941, the British colonial government established the fishery department as a sub-branch of the agricultural department, with a view to exploring and exploring the enormous gains in aquatic food resources. Altogether, the first phase of agricultural development in Nigeria which represents the colonial era, witnessed massive investment in the four major aspects of farming which includes, crop farming, livestock, poultry and fishery. The abundance in output from these sectors, which characterised the first phase of agricultural development in Nigeria was sufficient enough to guarantee a high level of food security, both for local consumption and for exportation purposes (Nwankwo, 2009; Ayuba, 2015).

Following the exit of the British colonial administration from Nigeria in 1960, the indigenous leadership class who inherited the task of governance from the colonial government officials made attempts at sustaining the legacies of the British colonial administration. In the aspect of ensuring food sufficiency and security, the Nigerian political leadership class at both federal and state levels initiated various agricultural policies and programmes aimed at vigorously boosting food production. Hence, this was geared towards achieving the purposes of providing significantly adequate food for local consumption and also to convert same to a reliable and prolific source of revenue for the government, as well as constituting a sustainable source of income for career farmers. The post-colonial agricultural development initiative was basically rural development strategy oriented and was statutorily incorporated into the periodic national development plans. The motive behind this was conceived against the backdrop of the awareness of the vast and untapped economic potentials in Nigeria's rural communities. The profundity of the economic resources in this context is mostly defined in terms of the vastness of arable land mass, rivers and creeks, essential for agricultural activities, necessary for ensuring food availability, sufficiency and sustainability for the whole country. Therefore, the various agricultural policies and programmes enacted by the post-colonial Nigerian government have always been an expression of the different strategies and methods of boosting food security in the country through rural development approach (Agoda, 2022).

The Land Settlement Scheme was a national agricultural policy and strategy, introduced in Nigeria in 1959. The policy was initially promulgated to exclusively serve the western region of the country. However, by 1960, following Nigeria's political independence, the scheme assumed a national assignment. The programme was created with the fundamental aim of apportioning portions of farmlands to prospective commercial farmers. These lands were acquired from native authorities by the government and then allocated to intending farmers. More so, the task of providing farmlands, the financing of farming activities, training programme and the take-off grants that would be given to the intending farm settlers constituted the responsibilities expected to be fully borne by the government. The core objectives of the farm settlement scheme in Nigeria consisted in the effort to effectively intervene in issues surrounding ancestral land ownership and hence, authoritatively effect a lasting solution to the inherent impediments to the allocation of lands for agricultural purposes. Other objectives include the introduction of modern farming techniques, achieve tremendous increase in agricultural production and the enhancement of employment opportunities and deserving source of income for young school leavers (Ayuba, 2015).

The impact of the Land Settlement Scheme on agricultural development in Nigeria was richly rewarding. The scheme provided a significant growth in employment opportunities among young school leavers. Hence, the figure had grown from 2.6% in 1960, to 4.4% in 1963. This development was a product of the introduction by the scheme, of agricultural extension programmes where young school leavers were trained in modern farming techniques, with the full sponsorship of the government. Also, through the

farm settlement scheme, the monetary value of the country's GDP rose from \$4.47million in 1961 to \$6.37 million in 1966. Most importantly, the farm settlement scheme was very significant in tremendously boosting food production in Nigeria. It profoundly increased domestic food production and significantly boosted export trade, most especially in the areas of cocoa, palm oil and timber production. By 1965, the contribution of cocoa and timber production in Nigeria's export trade through the farm settlement scheme grew from 13% in 1961 to 46% (Idika, 2020).

Following the rising spate of crude oil exploration, exploitation and sales (local and foreign), preeminent attention on agricultural development in Nigeria, in the 70s started declining at a gradual but sustained pace. The immediate consequence of this development became evident in low level of food production throughout the country. Thus, that had led to an increase in dependence on food importation. To mitigate this rising tide, in 1975, the government of the late military Head of State, Murtala Mohammed initiated a national agricultural development programme known as Operation Feed the Nation (OFN). However, the programme (OFN), was formally launched in 1976. The central objective of the programmes was anchored on the pressing need to address the rising cost of food commodities in Nigerian markets. Incidentally, the income capacity of many Nigerians, both in urban and rural areas could not conveniently afford such trends of continuous increase in the price of food commodities. In order to de-emphasise reliance on food importation, the government, through this medium resolved to adopt home-grown alternative to food production and sufficiency through massive investment in agricultural development. Therefore, the OFN programme was launched with a view to mitigating the severity of food price related crisis, by maximizing the enormous agricultural opportunities in Nigeria's rural communities. The strategies adopted by the OFN programme include the encouragement of prospective farmers through the provision of sufficient financial grants, mechanised farming implements, adequate training of prospective farmers on modern farming technologies and the cultivation of crop varieties with a view to enhancing emphasis on eating good and balanced nutrition. Other strategies also involved the introduction of effective pest control mechanism and mass procurement and distribution of agricultural incentives among farmers in rural areas (Familugba, 2016; Esohen, 2018).

The Growth Enhancement Support Scheme (GESS) was a rural agricultural programme that was conceived and introduced in 2012 under the administration of Nigeria's former president, Goodluck Jonathan. This scheme was conceived and introduced on the heels of the awareness of the immense role, enormous but quality fertilizer procurement and supply has in assisting sub-saharan African countries to attain food security. As part of its Agricultural transformation agenda, the central emphasis of this scheme hinged on liberalising fertilizer distribution, benefit even to the small-scale farmers in rural areas, with a view to boosting food sufficiency and improve income generation among rural dwellers. In the administration of GESS, the duty of the government changed from being exclusively responsible for direct procurement and distribution of fertilizer, to assuming the role of paternal facilitators of procurement, regulation of fertilizer quality, as well as encouraging the maximum involvement of the private-sector in the fertilizer value chain. Using this platform, federal and state governments were statutorily under obligation each, to contribute 25 percent of the total cost of fertilizer procurement, hence, implying a 50 percent subsidy benefit for both small- and large-scale rural farmers in the country. In terms of registering farmers to participate in the scheme, it was the jurisdictional responsibility of governments at the state and local levels. As a result, the two levels of government registered a total number of 3.91 million farmers in 2012; 9.5 million farmers in 2013 and 10.47 million farmers in 2014 (Agoda, 2022).

The administration of agricultural development policies and programmes since the post-colonial experience in Nigeria have remained ineffective and have continued to fall short of achieving an appreciable level of food sufficiency and security. These inabilities are however, attributed to series of recorded failures and deficiencies in the implementation of sound and very well-conceived agricultural policies and programmes. The implementation of the above reviewed agricultural development programmes like the Farm Settlement Scheme, Operation Feed the Nation and the Growth Enhancement Support Scheme were blighted by issues relating to poor funding, poor level of commitment on the part of

the government, to agricultural development efforts, due to the discovery of crude oil in commercial quantity, recurring challenges of insecurity and the overall system of corruption in the agricultural development value chain. The inability of the Nigerian state to address the institutional failings in agricultural development efforts has continued to give rise to a persistent trend of food insecurity in Nigeria. Hence, it is on record that the number of food insecure Nigerians significantly increased from 66.2 million in the first quarter of 2023 to 100 million in the first quarter of 2024. Also, data from the World Food Programme (WFP) shows that 43.7 million Nigerians in the second quarter of 2024 are living in acute hunger (Tunji, 2024).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Karl Marx theory of Economic Determinism. Basically, Economic Determinism theory is centred on the historic impression that the collaborative dimensions of a society's economy determine and define all aspects of political, social, religious and cultural life of such a society. The values on which Karl Marx propounded his theory of economic determinism, according to Egbo (2015), consist in the following:

- a) The existence of humans as it pertains to social relationships is traceable to a historically proven interest to engage in and benefit from economic activities which have their fundamental root in the satisfaction of the basic needs of humans.
- b) That there must exist in any politically governed society where sovereignty defines its existence, a lawfully recognized institution which in this case, might mean a government, which should be saddled with the statutory responsibility of harnessing and distributing the resources of the state for the common and equitable benefit of the people.
- c) That the degree of economic well-being of the people constitute a reliable yardstick for measuring the degree of all-round social stability with which a society is adjudged.
- d) That the ability of a society's leadership class to command the loyalty and cooperation of its subjects is tied to the survival rating and economic well-being of the people.

According to Mukherjee and Ramaswamy (2011), Karl Marx developed his theory of economic determinism from his analysis of the ideology of dialectical materialism. Marx perceived of dialectical materialism as an ideology which presumes that political and historical happening result from social struggles for survival and by extension, for a conducive material wellbeing. Thus, struggle in this context is seen as being triggered by basic material needs such as food and shelter. Mukherjee and Ramaswamy (2011) further emphasised that Karl Marx used the concept of Dialectical Materialism to explain the consequences of the State's abandonment of its fundamental obligation of efficiently, equitably and cautiously administering the resources of the state to satisfactorily meet the basic needs of man. Hence, state failure in this context represents the ensuing state of prevalence in the level of hunger, destitution, poverty, crime and other indices of social misnomer.

The relevance of Karl Marx theory of Economic Determinism can be appreciated on the basis of its ability to ideologically explain the relationship between institutional mechanisms to satisfy the economic needs of the Nigerian masses and the actual economic wellbeing and status of the people. The theory helped in analytically unearthing the statutory responsibility of the Nigerian government with regards to addressing the challenges of food security through effective system of agricultural development. The theory of Economic Determinism as propounded by Karl Marx was also instrumental to the unmasking of the factors responsible for the inability of the government to successfully but sustainably address the recurring challenges of food sufficiency and security through intensive agricultural development strides.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Factors Responsible for the Declining State of Agricultural Development as it Relates to Food Security in Nigeria Between 2015 and 2023

Most scholarly researches have revealed a lot of technical and administrative factors which have continued to sabotage and frustrate agricultural development strides in Nigeria. Some of the technical

factors identified in this context include, poor land tenure system, low level of irrigation farming, climate change and land degradation, low technology, high post-harvest losses, etc. On the other hand, the administrative factors observed include, poor system of distribution of agricultural inputs like seeds, fertilizers, energy, veterinary drugs, farming machines like tractors and processing plants. Others include, high production cost, poor financing, poor land tenure system, etc. Admittedly, the combined impact of these factors has been known to be responsible for the obvious decline in agricultural production in Nigeria. Such, undoubtedly has accounted for reasons for the growing incidences and trends in food insufficiency, declining level of food availability, low level of accessibility and a diminishing food security status. Also, it has been observed that both the technical and administrative factors responsible for the unsuccessful realisation of agricultural developmental strides in Nigeria during the period under study, are blamable on the government's inability to translate agricultural policy statements into tangible actions, having implication in food production sufficiency, availability and accessibility (Agama, 2020; Alawu, 2020).

According to Esohen (2018), the issues raised above constitute the integrals of a broader body of factors which include:

- i. Administrative Lapses/Incompetence
- ii. Corruption
- iii. Insecurity

Administrative Lapses/Incompetence: Accordingly, Esohen (2018) informed that administrative lapses and incompetence in this context entail all issues pertaining to defective policy implementation plan, which include poor future and weather forecasting, poor climatically-inclined disaster control mechanisms, poor pest control mechanism, inadequate supply of fertilizer and other farming implements, inadequate funding, defective policy on land tenure system and high cost of production due to erratic energy supply and unfavourable government legislations. Hence, Agoda (2022) observed that administrative inadequacies revolving around implementation plan flaws, characterised the operationalisation of most agricultural policies and programmes in Nigeria. In their separate contribution, Alawu (2020) maintained that the administration of fertilizer supply to commercial farmers in Nigeria has always been blighted, owing to the seemingly lack of proper decentralisation of fertilizer supply chain throughout the country. Thus, according to Alawu (2020), such has continued to have implication in low level of accessibility of fertilizers to intending farmers throughout the country. In addition, Ezeoke (2021) asserted that one of the real causes of poor level of availability and accessibility of fertilizers by farmers in Nigeria can also be attributed to the high cost of the product. Hence, Ezeoke (2021) argued that the reason behind this could be linked to the impact of the prevalent exchange rates on the price of fertilizers. Thus, according to Ikpoto (2023), by year 2021, statistics from AfricaFertiliser showed that the official volume of fertilizer imports to Nigeria increased by 65% to 706, 922MT. Also, Ikpoto (2023) informed that statistics from AfricaFertiliser indicated that what Nigeria spends annually on the importation of raw materials for fertilizer production accounts for over 75%. This development, according to Ikpoto (2023) makes the cost of fertilizers unaffordable. The consequence, as would be expected always has a negative impact on food production

In the opinion of Familugba (2016), the lack of administrative proactiveness on the part of the Nigerian government with regards to effectively administering agricultural development is also evident in the paucity or deteriorating state of mechanised system of farming. Hence, according to Familugba (2016), the seemingly low level of mechanised system of farming in Nigeria has frustrated the country's effort to fully embrace and explore the benefits of modern agricultural practice. This, according to Familugba (2016), has been impacting negatively in achieving a sustainable height of food security in Nigeria. To this end, Komolafe (2018) observed that Nigeria's agricultural mechanisation status ranks among the lowest in the world, at 0.027 horsepower per hectare. This is viewed as being far from the FAO's recommendation of 1.5 horsepower per hectare. Also, according to the revelation made by the National Agricultural Technology and Innovation Policy, 2022-2027, despite the \$1.2bn Green Imperative Programme launched by the Federal Government in 2020, Nigeria still ranks among the lowest in terms

of mechanised system of agriculture globally. Hence, in Nigeria, it is statistically established that 70-90% of cultivated land is worked by hand tools, while 10-25% is operated by draught animals. On the other hand, 5-15% is mechanically operated. In the year 2022, the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD), disclosed that there were over 10,000 grounded tractors spread across the 36 states of the federation and the FCT (Tunji, 2022).

Corruption: According to Esohen (2018), systemic corruption constitutes one of the major factors sabotaging and frustrating the realisation of maximum success in agricultural developmental strides in Nigeria. Systemic corruption in this context, according to Esohen (2018), is suggestive of the extent to which official mischievousness and sharp practices tend to characterise the existence and operational style of institutions of governance in Nigeria. Esohen (2018), further emphasised that acts of corruption in the administration of agricultural development policies and programmes in Nigeria are usually exhibited at their implementation stage. Hence, this is the stage where in the course of allocating the various aspects of material and financial resources needed for the execution of agricultural development schemes, public office holders, either in the capacity of political office holders or public servants, indulge in morally unwholesome practices that tend to sabotage or frustrate the realisation of agricultural development objectives. To this end, Tunji (2022), noted that the failure of the Green Imperative Programme of the previous administration of former President Muhammadu Buhari failed to achieve desired results, owing to the impact of corruption in its operationalisation. Hence, Tunji (2022), observed that the earmarking and subsequent disbursement of \$1.2bn fund for the execution of the Green Imperative Programme did not reflect its actual utilisation. Thus, Tunji (2022), informed that the splitting and allocation of the said fund among the various states and local governments provided an avenue for misappropriations, embezzlement and diversion of fund by corrupt-tending government functionaries. In addition, Tunji (2024), informed that as part of efforts to carry out the step-by-step implementation of the National Agricultural Technology and Innovation Policy, 2022-2027, data from the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD), revealed that the over N450bn allocated for the procurement, repairs and constant maintenance of heavy agricultural equipment and machines like the tractors, harvesters, excavators, fertilizer spreaders, etc. was misappropriated and unaccounted for.

Insecurity: Accordingly, Esohen (2018), identified insecurity as a major factor militating against agricultural development, and by extension, maximum level of food production, sufficiency and security in Nigeria. In this context, Ahamba (2020) observed that the menacing activities of terrorism, banditry and kidnapping have been responsible for the sacking of most farming communities in Nigeria, especially in the northern part of the country with the largest number of farming communities. The routine attacks by insurgents on communities where agricultural activities take place in large commercial status has over time, been discouraging and threatening to full-time farmers from accessing their farms. According to International Crisis Group (2018), between June 2015 and May 2018, the Boko Haram and Fulani herdsmen onslaught against farming communities in the rural areas of north eastern and northcentral parts of Nigeria had accounted for over 26, 500 fatalities. The report from this study further claimed that 71% of these attacks were executed in rural farmlands and bushes where both subsistence and commercial agricultural activities take place. A study carried out by Aderounmu et al (2021), indicated that in most cases, these terror sects impose heavy taxes on farmers to authorize and guarantee their access to their farms. Hence, Aderounmu (2021) informed that occasionally, the terrorists charge farmers exorbitant taxes ranging from N70million to N10million, depending on the size of farmlands. Consequently, affected farmers abandon their farming activities. In some cases, farmers who accept such a condition sell their farm produce at very high rate due to insufficient harvest.

The Consequences of the Declining State of Agricultural Development as it Pertains to Food Security in Nigeria Between 2015 and 2023.

Findings from a series of research on the impact of the deteriorating status of agricultural development on food security in Nigeria during the period covered by this study, indicate an alarming degree of national socio-economic meltdown. This condition has become the more loudly expressed in terms of its infamous

ability to cripple the standard of living of majority of Nigerians. To this end, Onyeali (2022), identified three major consequences of the declining state of agricultural development as it affects food security in Nigeria. These issues, according to Onyeali (2022), include the following:

- i. High Rate of Food Importation
- ii. High Rate of Poverty and Hunger
- iii. A Concomitant Rise in the Level of Malnutrition, Diseases and Social Malaise.

High Rate of Food Importation: According to Onyeali (2022), on account of the inability of the Nigerian government to initiate and implement potent agricultural policies, efficacious enough to boost national food production, the resolve to resort to food importation becomes inevitable. Hence, Magaji (2020) observed that Nigeria depends in a most part, on the importation of foods that ordinarily should be grown in the country due to the sufficient availability of arable lands and the existence of an enormous population of physically resilient individuals who can actively take part in farming activities to boost sufficient food production, both for local consumption and for purposes of export, to boost the country's GDP and foreign earnings. According to Magaji (2020), some of these imported foods include rice, yam, beans, fish, meat, wheat, maize, milk, tomatoes, etc. It is on record that from 2015 to 2018, the Nigerian state has been making an annual expense of \$3 to \$5 billion on the importation of food crops like rice, beans, wheat, groundnut, fish, and other processed foods such as flour, noodles, tomato paste, etc. (Obiechina, 2019). In 2019 and 2020, it was reported that Nigeria spent N959 billion and N1.2 trillion respectively on food importation. In the year 2021, it was reported that Nigeria imported \$9 billion worth of food. It was also disclosed that cereal crops alone accounted for the largest portion, involving a figure that was up to \$3 billion. In 2022, the money spent on food importation surged to N1.9 trillion (NBS, 2024). To this end, Onyeali (2022) noted that it was a misnomer for a country where the availability of agricultural land in the northern part of the country alone is enough to sustainably feed the entire West African sub-continent, depends on the importation of cereal crops like maize and wheat to survive. Also, the NBS (2024) disclosed that in Q4 of 2023, food importation surged to N10.5 trillion, representing a 95.53 percent increase from the N6.47 trillion recorded in Q1 of 2023.

The data presented above clearly indicates that over the years, specifically between 2015 and 2023, funds spent on food importation in Nigeria have continued to experience a sustained increase. According to Aina (2023), in a space 'of four years, spanning 2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023, the Nigerian state has experienced an 80% surge in food importation. However, Aina (2023), remarked that in spite of the huge sums of money, annually expended on food importation, such alternative to making food available has over the years, proved to be ineffective and insufficient. Hence, according to Aina (2023), as at the last quarter of 2022, over 88.5 million Nigerians were still food insecure. In the opinion of Tunji (2024), "usually, the government can only make import, based on its financial capacity and will, and not taking into cognisance, the population strength of the target beneficiaries (the masses)" (p. 4).

High Rate of Poverty and Hunger: In this respect, Onyeali (2022), observed that with the exorbitant market prices of food commodities- a situation occasioned by foreign exchange rate realities, majority of Nigerian consumers can no longer afford to eat well. Hence, Onyeali (2022) further remarked that the effect of the weakness of the naira against foreign currencies, high custom duties as well as other forms of taxes paid on imported food items, undoubtedly force the market prices of food commodities to rise. In further analysis, Onyeali (2022) explained that due to the fact that the income capacity of majority of households and individuals in Nigeria is relatively inconsequential and cannot compete favourably with the realities provided by market forces, majority of Nigerian masses are thrown into abject poverty. In their separate opinion, Agama (2020) asserted that the limited access to food by majority of Nigerians is not only defined by the inability to have decent and quality meals, but also by extension, the inability to put food on their table. This is a situation where poverty has taken a grip on the lives of majority of Nigeria people. Hence, Agoda (2022), stressed that poverty in this context gives rise to widespread hunger and starvation.

Thus, below is a table showing Nigeria’s poverty rate between 2015 and 2023. This represented in percentages.

Poverty Rate In Nigeria Between 2015 and 2023

Year	Rate of Poverty
2015	69.01%
2016	43%
2017	41.4%
2018	40.1%
2019	40.1%
2020	42.%
2021	63%
2022	88.4%
2023	47%

Source: Oyedeji (2024)

The above table represents the gravity of poverty rate in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023. This situation has been known to be responsible for transforming into national hardship- the latter which constantly leads to excruciating national hunger. By statistics, it is on record that the rate of hunger in Nigeria has assumed a sustained progression over the years, from 2015 to 2023. Thus, the table below represents the percentage of the Nigerian population living in acute hunger and starvation, nationwide.

2015-2017- 12.3%

2016-2018- 13.6%

2017-2019- 15.1%

2018-2020- 17.3%

2019-2021- 19.8%

2020-2022- 21.3%

2021-2023- 31.5%

Source: Sasu, (2024).

A Concomitant Rise in the Level of Malnutrition, Diseases and Social Malaise: According to Onyeali (2022), on account of the prevalence of acute hunger, starvation and poor nutrition among majority of the Nigerian population, there has been a concomitant increase in the level of malnutrition, diseases and varied forms of social crisis like a hike in crime rate and overall insecurity of lives and property. A World Bank study (2024), revealed that 1 out of every ten sampled children in Nigeria suffer from diseases associated with malnutrition. Similarly, Tunji (2024) observed that the prevailing incidences of hunger and starvation among the majority of Nigeria’s population has persistently given rise to multidimensional forms of social ills and malaise like civic discontent, frustration, desperation, depression, stealing, internet fraud, burglary and other forms of insecurity of lives and property like kidnapping for ransom, cattle rustling and robbery. According to Tunji (2024), in any period of very severe national economic hardship, mostly indicated by widespread hunger and starvation, people tend to resort to all manner of vice to survive.

Measures to Maximally Improve Agricultural Development in Nigeria: Various steps have been adduced by researchers on the measures to improve agricultural production, with a view to achieving sustainability in food security in Nigeria Undoubtedly, authors like Alawu (2020) and Ezeoke (2021) stress that the various measures and approaches are technically expected to be realised through improved provision of technologically advanced farming implements land methods like tractors, processing plants, cultivators, harrows, fertilizers, irrigation, thresher, sprayers, institutional reforms of the land tenure system, etc. However, Onyeali (2022), impressed that the workability of the above-mentioned technical methods of improving agricultural production in Nigeria, is anchored on three key institutional strategies

of increased funding of the agricultural sector, agricultural policy/programme implementation effectiveness/transparency and increased emphasis on the security of lives and property.

- a. **Increased Funding of the Agricultural Sector:** In this aspect, Onyeali (2022), informed that the bringing into fruition, the approaches, methods and attempts at revamping the agricultural sector in Nigeria depends in part, on sufficient allocation of financial resources. Thus, the process of procuring and acquiring modern farming technologies and equipment, as well as all the sundry logistics required to implement sound agricultural policies, must involve adequate funding. Specifically, Ikpoto (2023), advocated for an increase in budgetary allocation to the agricultural sector by the federal and state governments. Hence, Tunji (2024), decried the condition where the Nigerian state is yet to comply with the African Union's Maputo Declaration of 2003 which recommended a minimum standard of 10% of national budgets to the agricultural sector. Regrettably though, the national budgetary allocations to the agricultural sector in Nigeria for the years 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024 and 2025 by percentage are 2.83%, 2.11%, 1.62%, 1.25%, 1.16%, 1.32% and 1.7% respectively (Nwachukwu, 2024). In their separate opinion, Ezeoke (2021), advocated for private sector partnership with the government in agricultural development funding.
- b. **Agricultural Policy/Programme Implementation Effectiveness/Transparency:** In this context, Onyeali (2022) rationalised for effective and efficient agricultural policy implementation mechanism to boost massive food production. Hence, Onyeali (2022), impressed that there must exist, political will on the part of the government to effectively and uncompromisingly, through its bureaucratic structure, transform the various agricultural policy proposals and ideals into tangible actions that would entail a comprehensive and sustained trends of farming activities to boost food production. According to Agoda (2022), transparency in agricultural policy/programme implementation entails the preparedness by agricultural policy makers and executors to faithfully and honestly commit the financial resources earmarked for agricultural development into actionable instruments. By implication, Agoda (2022), emphasised that the implementation of agricultural policies and programmes should connote the display of accountability by executors of agricultural policies and programmes, with regards to the management of funds. In essence, Agoda (2022) stressed the need to tackle corruption in the process of policy execution.
- c. **Increased Emphasis on the Security of Lives and Property:** According to Onyeali (2022), there should be heightened effort by the government at both federal and states level to confront the growing menace of banditry, kidnappings and all other forms of terror attacks throughout the country, especially in the northern part of the country where large scale farming practices take place. Hence, Agoda (2022) remarked that un confronted insecurity challenges in a country has the unfortunate capacity to undermine efforts aimed at enhancing food production through comprehensive improvement in agricultural activities.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Factors Responsible for the Declining State of Agricultural Development as it Relates to Food Security in Nigeria

The study, based on findings from reviewed scholarly works, revealed that administrative lapses and incompetence, institutional corruption and insecurity, constitute the factors that militate against the realisation of effective administration of agricultural development in Nigeria during the period under study. The study disclosed that the trends of administrative incompetence and lapses in this context is expressed in the inability of agricultural policy makers and implementers to effectively manage the various limitations to achieving success in the management provide for and effectively manage the various agricultural developmental strides. These include, poor land tenure system, low level of irrigation farming, climate change and land degradation, low technology, high post-harvest losses, poor system of

distribution of agricultural inputs like seeds, fertilizers, energy, veterinary drugs, farming machines like tractors and processing plants, etc.

In the aspect of corruption, this study established a finding based on the reviewed works of other researchers and published official documents that the implementation of agricultural policies and programmes in Nigeria during the years covered by this study, was adversely frustrated by the corrupt tendencies of public office holders. This study disclosed the fact that indulgence in acts of misappropriation, embezzlement, diversion of agricultural development project funds, as well as other forms of sabotage of policy implementation processes, tend to frustrate the realisation of agricultural development efforts. This in turn, continues to worsen the already deteriorating state of food security in Nigeria, with consequences manifesting in high level of excruciating hunger and starvation. In addition, it is a finding in this study that acts of terrorism, banditry, cattle rustling and kidnapping constitute security huge threat to commercial farmers, especially in the northern part of the country with very vast agricultural development opportunities. Such development, based on the findings in this study adversely hampered agricultural activities, hence, farmers could not access their farms. The study further disclosed that even in situations where the terror groups allow farmers access to their farms, they were not without very unpleasant and expensive conditions. Consequently, this has severally led to very poor agricultural yield and harvest throughout the country, thereby leading to food scarcity and outrageously high prices of food commodities.

The Consequences of the Declining State of Agricultural Development as it Pertains to Food Security in Nigeria

Findings in this study revealed that issues like high rate of food importation, high rate of poverty and hunger, as well as a simultaneous rise in the level of malnutrition, outbreak of diseases and social malaise/vices, constitute the major consequences of the declining state of agricultural development in Nigeria during the years covered by this study. Hence, this study revealed that with the evidently level of food security- a situation occasioned by the decadent state of agricultural development in the country, a rise in the level of food importation becomes inevitable. Again, this study revealed that with the unfavourable exchange rate at the international market which is evident in the sustained depreciation of the naira, the market prices of food commodities become too costly for majority of Nigerians to afford. The result, according to the finding in this study is usually demonstrated in widespread hunger. By extension also, the study revealed that the attendant incidence of high level of poverty and hunger has always given rise to a myriad of social ills and vices like frustration, desperation, destitution, depression, criminality, etc.

Measures to Maximally Improve Agricultural Development in Nigeria

Based on findings from credible sources, this study revealed that improved funding, effective and transparent process of implementation of agricultural policies and programmes by the government, as well as increased emphasis on thoroughly combating security challenges should constitute the measures to maximally improve agricultural development in Nigeria. the study reviewed the scholarly contributions of authors like Ezeoke (2021) and Agoda (2022), who harped on the need for public office holders in Nigeria to shun tendencies of corruption, exhibit a high sense of political will, dedication, commitment and competence in the course of executing agricultural programmes and policies so as to achieve, guarantee and sustain an appreciable level of food security in the country.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The foundation of survival of any society is laid on the economic value and wellbeing of such a society. Ordinarily, the relevance of a society's economic potency, buoyancy and wellbeing is fundamentally expressed in the ability for its citizenry to feed well with good nutrition. In other words, a sustainable food security constitutes a sure primary criterion for measuring a thriving economy. On the other hand, a weak or prostrate national economic base is usually indicated in low agricultural production, leading to

food insufficiency and overall short term, medium term and long-term trends of food insecurity. As a result, to realise such a national objective, a determined effort by the leadership of any nation-state to improve agricultural production to boost food sufficiency.

In attempt to appraise the impact of agricultural development on food security in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023, this study explored a myriad of unlimited benefits of food security in guaranteeing the economic life and wellbeing of the citizenry of a country. The study, while appraising the various agricultural policies initiated and implemented by past governments, uncovered that the failing status of agricultural development in Nigeria is inseparably linked to the poor and incompetent approaches to the execution of agricultural policies and programmes. The study identified examined administrative lapses/incompetence, institutional corruption and the yet-to-be tamed challenges of insecurity as some of the key factors militating against the successful administration of agricultural development policies and programmes. Thus, the Nigerian state has over time, been confronted with the most excruciating trends of food insecurity as a result. As comprehensively observed in this study, the consequences of the deteriorating status of food security in Nigeria has plunged the country into various forms of social anomalies ranging from poverty, hunger, diseases, anxiety, depression to criminal activities. Accordingly, this study has also identified and explored various strategies and measures to curb the problem of food insecurity through a determined effort aimed at revitalising the agricultural sector.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- I. There should be an improved institutional emphasis on increased funding for the agricultural sector. This is expected to entail a statutorily enabled annual increase in budgetary allocation by states and at the federal level. Besides, there should be emphasis on government-private sector partnership in funding the agricultural sector in Nigeria.
- II. There should be an institutional mechanism for effective implementation of agricultural policies and programmes. This is also expected to embody the need to curb the perpetration of corrupt practices by public office holders who are statutorily saddled with the responsibility of executing agricultural policies and programmes.
- III. The government should prioritise combating and winning the war against the challenges of insecurity which manifest in the form of kidnapping, banditry, cattle rustling and other forms of terror attacks.

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